

Acoustical studies of some novel antimicrobially active 3d-metal-Schiff base complexes

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Studies of ultrasonic velocity and density have been made in solutions of furfurylidene-4-aminoacetanilide (FAA), 3-nitrobenzylidene-2-amino-4-chlorophenol (NAP) and 4-chlorobenzylidene-2-amino-4-chlorophenol (CAP) and their Co^{II}, Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} complexes in methanol at 303.15 K. The values of apparent molar volume, acoustic impedance, adiabatic compressibility, intermolecular free length, molar sound velocity (Rao's constant), molar compressibility (Wada's constant) and solvation number have been computed from density and ultrasonic data. The results are discussed in the light of solute-solvent interaction and structural effects on the solvent in solution.

Density and ultrasonic velocity provide interesting information regarding the ion-ion, ion-solvent and solvent-solvent interactions and also on structural effects of solute and solvent in solution¹. Solvation and various acoustical parameters of octahedral Co^{III} complexes in water + DMSO mixture have been studied by Dash *et al.*². Kawaizumi *et al.*³ studied the partial molar volume and partial molar adiabatic compressibility of ethylenediamine complexes in water. Literature provides very little information about such studies on the solutions of metal complexes⁴. It is worthwhile to study the interaction of synthesized bioactive antimicrobial Schiff base ligands with 3d-metal ions.

Present study aims at the measurement of density and ultrasonic velocity of furfurylidene-4-aminoacetanilide (FAA), 3-nitrobenzylidene-2-amino-4-chlorophenol (NAP), 4-chlorobenzylidene-2-amino-4-chlorophenol (CAP) complexes (M = Co^{II}/Ni^{II}/Cu^{II}) in methanol at 303.15 K. Various acoustical parameters have been evaluated for these complexes, which may be utilized to understand the interaction of metal chelates in solution.

Theoretical :

Apparent molar volume has been calculated from the density data using the expression,

$$\phi_v = -\frac{M_2}{d_1} - \left(\frac{d_1 - d_0}{Cd_1} \right) \quad (1)$$

where C is the concentration, d_0 and d_1 are the densities of solution and solvent respectively, and M_2 is the molecular weight of solute.

Rao's constant, adiabatic compressibility, Wada's con-

stant, intermolecular free length, solvation number and acoustic impedance have been computed using the relations,

$$R = V U^{1/3} \quad (2)$$

$$\beta = \frac{1}{U^2 d_0} \quad (3)$$

$$W = V \beta_s^{-1/7} \quad (4)$$

$$L_f = K \beta_s \quad (5)$$

$$S_n = n_1/n_2 [1 - (\beta_s/\beta_s^0)] \quad (6)$$

$$Z = d_0 U \quad (7)$$

where, R , V , β_s^0 , β_s , n_1 , n_2 , K , W , L_f , S_n , U and Z are the Rao's constant, molar volume, adiabatic compressibility of solvent and solution, number of moles of solvent and solute, Jacobson constant, Wada's constant, intermolecular free length, solvation number, ultrasonic velocity and acoustic impedance, respectively.

Results and Discussion

The density, ultrasonic velocity, apparent molar volume, acoustic impedance, molar sound velocity (Rao's constant)⁵, molar compressibility (Wada's constant)⁶, intermolecular free length, adiabatic compressibility and solvation number of ligands (Schiff bases), metal ions and metal complexes are presented in Table 1.

These values for solutions of complexes, ligands (Schiff base) and metal chlorides (methanol as solvent) have been found to be different. This reflects molecular interactions between solute and solvent. This further indicates the interaction between metal ion and ligand using methanol as

Table 1. Values of density (d_0), ultrasonic velocity (U), apparent molar volume (ϕ_v), acoustic impedance (Z), adiabatic compressibility (β_s), Rao's constant (R), Wada's constant (W), intermolecular free length (L_f) and solvation number (S_n) for FAA, NAP, CAP and metal chlorides at 303.15 K

Concn. mol dm ⁻³	$d_0 \times 10^{-3}$ kg m ⁻³	U m s ⁻¹	$\phi_v \times 10^5$ m ³ mol ⁻¹	$Z \times 10^{-3}$ kg m ⁻² s ⁻¹	$\beta_s \times 10^{11}$ m ² N ⁻¹	$R \times 10^6$	$W \times 10^6$	L_f Å	S_n
C₁₃H₁₂N₂O₂ (FAA)									
0.01	1.0010	1425	310.05	1426.42	49.20	2566.12	4856.34	0.4526	164.25
0.005	1.0001	1420	593.00	1420.00	49.59	2565.39	4852.63	0.4562	327.24
0.0025	0.9992	1416	1170.51	1414.86	49.91	2565.34	4846.70	0.4590	649.66
[Co(C₁₃H₁₂N₂O₂)(H₂O)₂].Cl₂									
0.01	1.0019	1435	326.08	1437.72	48.47	4437.50	8396.77	0.4459	166.45
0.005	1.0013	1429	633.06	1430.82	48.90	4434.03	8390.59	0.4489	330.84
0.0025	1.0007	1424	1286.50	1424.99	49.28	4431.51	8379.34	0.4534	658.08
[Ni(C₁₃H₁₂N₂O₂)(H₂O)₂].Cl₂									
0.01	1.0028	1446	317.34	1450.04	47.69	4442.61	8425.08	0.4388	169.06
0.005	1.0022	1442	628.75	1445.16	47.98	4441.10	8416.27	0.4414	336.32
0.0025	1.0017	1437	1247.59	1439.44	48.34	4438.23	8397.03	0.4448	668.64
[Cu(C₁₃H₁₂N₂O₂)(H₂O)₂].Cl₂									
0.01	1.0036	1462	317.17	1467.26	46.62	4509.67	8527.25	0.4288	172.00
0.005	1.0032	1455	611.91	1459.66	47.08	4504.16	8518.16	0.4332	342.27
0.0025	1.0027	1449	1210.81	1452.91	47.50	4500.34	8502.24	0.4369	678.54
C₁₃H₉N₂O₃Cl (NAP)									
0.01	0.9998	1370	338.83	1369.72	53.21	3073.64	5847.11	0.4894	154.49
0.005	0.9992	1365	652.47	1363.90	53.76	3071.74	5842.89	0.4940	301.97
0.0025	0.9986	1361	1270.60	1359.09	54.04	3070.58	5841.61	0.4968	600.33
[Co(C₁₃H₉N₂O₃Cl)₂(H₂O)₂]									
0.01	1.0014	1386	359.14	1387.94	51.92	7195.94	13684.64	0.4774	156.40
0.005	1.0011	1381	661.46	1382.51	52.34	7189.44	13673.56	0.4811	310.39
0.0025	1.0002	1375	1289.18	1375.27	52.86	7185.46	13667.57	0.4857	614.77
[Ni(C₁₃H₉N₂O₃Cl)₂(H₂O)₂]									
0.01	1.0016	1390	359.71	1392.22	51.69	7198.85	13688.34	0.4747	157.30
0.005	1.0009	1384	667.32	1385.24	52.18	7193.51	13679.05	0.4793	311.59
0.0025	1.0004	1380	1280.95	1380.55	52.46	7190.16	13674.81	0.4820	619.58
[Cu(C₁₃H₉N₂O₃Cl)₂].2H₂O									
0.01	1.0019	1395	356.75	1397.65	51.26	7258.85	13801.21	0.4710	158.50
0.005	1.0013	1391	660.05	1392.80	51.69	7256.26	13794.23	0.4747	314.60
0.0025	1.0007	1386	1278.66	1386.97	52.09	7251.81	13787.27	0.4784	624.39
C₁₃H₉NC₁₂O (CAP)									
0.01	1.0015	1408	320.36	1410.25	50.36	2978.12	5641.09	0.4633	160.77
0.005	1.0012	1402	622.69	1403.68	50.81	2975.11	5639.12	0.4674	319.41
0.0025	1.0006	1395	1217.55	1395.84	51.35	2971.94	5632.23	0.4724	632.82
[Co(C₁₃H₉NC₁₂O)₂]									
0.01	1.0018	1415	349.73	1417.55	49.85	6602.98	12501.59	0.4568	162.45
0.005	1.0013	1410	652.05	1411.83	50.23	6598.45	12494.17	0.4621	323.03
0.0025	1.0008	1401	1279.80	1402.12	50.53	6587.62	12482.29	0.4685	637.63
[Ni(C₁₃H₉NC₁₂O)₂]									
0.01	1.0028	1429	333.83	1433.00	48.83	5897.96	12522.29	0.4485	165.46
0.005	1.0022	1425	628.40	1428.13	49.13	5895.94	12510.34	0.4525	329.64
0.0025	1.0019	1418	1242.84	1420.69	49.64	5888.07	12497.69	0.4554	653.27
[Cu(C₁₃H₉NC₁₂O)₂]									
0.01	1.0020	1423	342.05	1425.84	49.28	5948.30	12624.26	0.4494	163.97
0.005	1.0014	1419	644.37	1420.98	49.59	5946.31	12606.34	0.4547	326.64
0.0025	1.0008	1414	1260.65	1415.13	49.67	5943.14	12591.20	0.4582	648.46

Table-1 (contd.)

CoCl ₂ .6H ₂ O									
0.01	1.0039	1378	295.32	1389.37	52.45	2634.66	4996.02	0.4825	153.10
0.005	1.0035	1374	574.63	1378.90	52.76	2633.22	4993.65	0.4855	299.50
0.0025	1.0028	1368	1158.51	1371.83	53.29	2631.26	4989.32	0.4903	593.10
NiCl ₂ .6H ₂ O									
0.01	1.0037	1377	297.25	1382.09	52.54	2631.24	5000.91	0.4833	152.10
0.005	1.0032	1372	511.16	1376.39	52.95	2635.24	4997.20	0.4871	292.40
0.0025	1.0027	1367	1158.68	1370.69	53.40	2633.40	4994.18	0.4912	590.20
CuCl ₂ .2H ₂ O									
0.01	1.0045	1380	283.96	1386.22	52.27	1886.99	3577.65	0.4808	154.34
0.005	1.0040	1374	559.79	1379.49	52.75	1884.92	3574.30	0.4853	300.24
0.0025	1.0036	1369	1117.44	1373.92	53.16	1883.56	3570.45	0.4890	595.24

solvent medium.

The values of apparent molar volume are higher in comparison to those of ligands and metal ions. The values of apparent molar volume for metal complex systems decrease in the order : Ni-NAP > Co-NAP > Cu-NAP > Co-CAP > Cu-CAP > Ni-CAP > Co-FAA > Ni-FAA > Cu-FAA, in all the three concentrations. Variation in apparent molar volume may be accounted to the size and geometrical arrangement of the metal complexes in solution. Apparent molar volume increases with decrease in concentration of solute indicating the decrease in stacking interaction between solute and solvent molecules⁷.

Values of ultrasonic velocity are comparatively higher for the metal (M = Co^{II}/Ni^{II}/Cu^{II}) complexes of FAA ligand. The values of ultrasonic velocity of various ligand systems are in order : CAP > FAA > NAP, for all the three concentrations. This order for metal ion system comes to be Cu > Co > Ni. On complexation, this order of ultrasonic velocity changes. This reflects about the impact of both ligands and metal ions on the solute-solvent interaction. Ultrasonic velocity and density increase with increase in concentration of the metal complexes. There is possibility of H-bond formation between methanol and the ligand/metal complex. The H-bond formation strengthens the intermolecular forces resulting in a decrease of compressibility and intermolecular free length, and increase of ultrasonic velocity, acoustic impedance and molar sound velocity. Eyring and Kincaid's model⁸ for sound propagation suggests that the intermolecular free length is a predominant factor in determining the variation of ultrasonic velocity in solution.

Compressibility gives account of the extent of ion-solvent molecular attraction and the resultant compactness. The compressibility values are comparatively lower for FAA ligand-metal complexes in comparison to NAP and CAP (which are of type ML₂). In this way, the former ligand complexes are in more compressed state than the latter. On com-

paring the compressibility values of metal complexes, this order comes to be M-NAP > Co-CAP > Cu-CAP > Ni-CAP > M-FAA (M = Cu < Ni < Co). In a comparison of the values of adiabatic compressibility of the one (same) ligand with different metal ions, the order remains same with ligand FAA and NAP (Cu < Ni < Co) except CAP (Ni < Cu < Co). The difference in β_s may be accounted to the nature of ligand (weak or strong field), stereoarrangement of ligand around the metal ion, non-spherical 3d-ions radii, solvation behavior, activation energy of solvation, influence of structure and size and distorted geometry of metal ion polyhedra in solution.

The above order of β_s follows that β_s depends upon the solvation layers/spheres formed around the metal complexes. A tight or dense solvation layer (primary and secondary) around an ion leads to decrease in β_s . The lowering of β_s varies with the effective size of the entering ligand in the metal complexes as the metal ion remains the same. Comparatively higher values of solvation number for FAA metal complexes suggest that these are more solvated than the other complexes. The solvation number is useful in understanding the structure-making and structure-breaking tendency of solute in a solvent. On comparing the values of solvation number of metal ion, ligand (Schiff base) and the corresponding metal complex, it has been found that the metal complex is more solvated than the ligand and their metal ions. The solvation number of the ligand is more than the metal ions alone, which may tentatively be accounted to the placement of solvent molecules in the interstitial spaces occurring in the metal chelate. Solvation number decreases in the order : M-FAA > Ni-CAP > Cu-CAP > Co-CAP > M-NAP (M = Cu > Ni > Co).

On comparing the solvation number values of different metal ions with same ligand, it has been found that the ligands NAP and FAA show similar behavior, i.e. Cu > Ni > Co, but in the case of CAP this order changes, i.e. Ni >

Cu > Co. This change in the behavior of CAP ligand may be attributed to the effect of LFSE, solvation energies and constitutional changes in symmetry.

In the solid phase all the ligands act as bidentate chelating agents and have C=N linkage. As a result of complexation, the values of the acoustical parameters like solvation number, adiabatic compressibility and intermolecular free length vary. This may be due to the changes and distortion in metal chelate's geometry. The solid phase study of the complexes reflects that complexes have 4 or 6 coordination number and metal-to-ligand stoichiometry is 1 : 1 for FAA and 1 : 2 for NAP and CAP.

Comparatively higher values of ultrasonic velocity, acoustic impedance and solvation number, and lower values of adiabatic compressibility and apparent molar volume for FAA ligand complexes may be due to ligand's structural effect and 1 : 1 stoichiometry with the metal ion. This makes the metal complexes of FAA ligand slightly more compact. The higher values of above parameters for CAP ligand-metal complexes than NAP ligand-metal complexes may be accounted to the comparatively stable five-membered ring. CAP ligand-metal complexes are more stable in comparison to NAP ligand-metal complexes. This may be due to electron-withdrawing tendency of NO₂ group than Cl group.

Most of the biological and pharmacological processes and reactions are accompanied in aqueous/semi-aqueous/non-aqueous media. There occurs a state of ligand competition among various ligands and metal ions. Many enzymatic processes are completed or mediated by metal ions. During transportation within the body system, biological situations of lipophilic and lipophobic/hydrophobic and hydrophilic occurs in GI and CV systems. A background knowledge of phenomenon of chelation and interaction in solutions helps in understanding the drug stabilization, drug gestation and mechanistic path for drug targeting, drug delivery and drug toxicity.

Lipids and polysaccharides are important constituents of cell membrane. Metal chelate is a species which bears polar and non-polar properties together, this makes them suitable for permeation to the cells and tissues. A differential changing in hydrophilicity and lipophilicity may probably lead to bringdown the solubility and permeability barriers of cells, which in turn enhance the bioavailability of chemotherapeutics on one hand and potentiality at another.

Such biomimetic and biosynergistic studies of metal chelates in solution may be useful in understanding the interaction of metal chelated biomolecules in the body

system. The studies on these lines may govern and guide for the subjects and problems, viz. pharmacokinetics and biomolecular dynamics in animal physiology vis-a-vis Inorganic medicinal chemistry. The metal-chelated drugs may appear as a solution in future for the complex problems like drug resistance in molecular biology⁹.

Experimental

Chemicals of standard purity (Fluka, CDH, Himedia and Loba) were used. Complexes of furfurylidene-4-aminoacetanilide (FAA), 3-nitrobenzylidene-2-amino-4-chlorophenol (NAP), 4-chlorobenzylidene-2-amino-4-chlorophenol (CAP) with Co^{II}, Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} were synthesized and characterized and their antimicrobial studies were reported elsewhere¹⁰.

The solutions of varying concentration of metal complexes were prepared on molarity basis. Density measurements were made with a bicapillary pycnometer accurate to 0.001%. At least five observations were taken for each solution in each determination and differences in any two readings did not exceed 0.02%. The measured density of solvent was $0.7920 \times 10^{-3} \text{ kg m}^{-3}$. The ultrasonic velocity of the solution was measured by using M-84 (Mittal Enterprises, New Delhi) instrument at a frequency of 2 MHz with an accuracy of 0.03% at constant temperature (303.15 K).

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